

Data Science in Solar storms and Aurora prediction

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Additional Keywords and Phrases: Solar storms, Solar wind, Solar flares, Ionosphere, Coronal mass ejections (CME), Aurora, Kp Index, OVATION, ACE (Advanced Composition Explorer)

1 INTRODUCTION

Solar activity has been a very important topic in the last decades. The earth is almost daily hit by solar storms which could sometimes result in a short disturbance or blackout of the electric power, telecommunication, damaging satellites and intense Auroras in the night sky. But when the intensity of solar storms goes higher than normal, the results are much worse. It has been proven that if nowadays a solar storm hits earth with the same magnitude as the strongest solar storm ever recorded, the consequences will be catastrophic, there would be human loss and it would cost trillions of dollars [1]. Therefore, it is essential to analyze the sun activity and try to predict the solar storms in order to have time to react and avoid catastrophes.

This paper describes the use of modern data science in the study of the sun activity and solar storm forecast.

2 SOLAR WINDS

Solar wind consists of charged particles (protons and electrons) that emanate from the sun at very high speed. This is better known as plasma and when near to the earth, it can have a speed of around 400 km per second (when low) and around 650 km per second (when high speed) [2] which, once entering the earth magnetic field, are being attracted to the poles. When these particles collide in the ionosphere with atoms and molecules, they are being transformed from kinetic energy into visible light, which results in the beautiful Aurora. The ionosphere is an electrified layer of the upper atmosphere, starting at 80 km till 640 kms and is a product of extreme ultraviolet radiation from the sun. The light we

get to see comes from charged atoms which collided with the solar wind particles. These release this energy in form of light. These wind particles will keep on colliding with other atoms, getting slower till around 100 km above Earth where it finally stops. The magnetosphere which is formed by the magnetic fields of the earth, protects Earth from particles traveling in space. The edge of this magnetosphere is being hit constantly by a lot of energy and from this, just a small part gets it through the atmosphere and even a smaller part will become a Northern Light. [3]. However, if the solar winds are strong enough, they form a solar storm, which depending on the intensity level, can reach the earth ground and cause massive damages in form of radiations and sudden high currents which can have severe consequences.

3 SOLAR WINDS MEASUREMENT

The solar winds can be measured by intensity and velocity. And when the interplanetary magnetic field strength is measured, data scientists can forecast how the effect on earth will be. The data can be measured in real-time by a satellite called DSCOVR (Deep Space Climate Observatory) and a NASA spacecraft called ACE (Advanced Composition Explorer) located at 1.6 million km from earth and can be seen in the figure below [4].

The Kp Index “Kennziffer Planetarische” [3] was introduced by a german scientist to explain the planetary geomagnetic disturbance and consequently predict the Aurora.

Figure 1 - In these 4 plots above can be seen data for a whole day. On the X axis is the hour of the day. From the bottom to the top, on the Y axis we can see the Kp, the temperature, the speed and the density of the solar wind.

4 PREDICTION OF THE AURORA

The OVATION (Oval Variation, Assessment, Tracking, Intensity, and Online Nowcasting) model is an empirical model which reveals the intensity of the aurora. In use since 2011 by the NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) and NASA. It was developed at the Johns Hopkins University, Applied Physics Laboratory. It uses the solar wind velocity and interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) as input and calculates three types of electron precipitation and the proton precipitation, which strongly correlates with the aurora. These measures are being taken from a single satellite maintained by NASA.

The OVATION Model [7] is a linear regression which fits the precipitation data. The solar wind function is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} d\Phi_{MP}/dt &= (v)(\sin^{8/3}(\theta_c/2))(B_T)(B_{MP}/B_T)^{1/3} \\ &= v^{1/3} B_T^{2/3} \sin^{8/3}(\theta_c/2) \end{aligned}$$

This function represents the rate magnetic flux is opened at the magnetopause. It involves the rate that IMF lines approach the magnetopause or solar wind velocity (v), interplanetary field magnitude (B_T), probability of IMF lines which do merge ($\sin^{8/3}(\theta_c/2)$) and the merging line length $(B_{MP}/B_T)^{1/3}$. [8]

The exponent for B_T provides confidence. If it would be smaller, like for example $1/2$, would reduce the variance across the 13 data runs used for this variable. As well, the Kp value is better by $B_T^{1/2}$ than $B_T^{2/3}$. Index from $\sin(8/3)$ was

as well tested and was the best performing in comparison with other exponents. It is as well an average over the details of magnetopause geometry, magnetic field in the magnetosheath and the merging rate.

Figure 2 - In the picture above, the Auroral Oval from the north can be seen

In the picture above, on the top right side can be read “Forecast Lead Time: 61 minutes”. This forecast comes from the OVATION model and gives exactly these 61 minutes to the users to know about this prediction. This prediction is accurate in 86% of the times, that means, when the aurora is predicted, there was actually an aurora (true positives). The overall model has an accuracy of 77%. Scientists that evaluated OVATION compared the predictions of the model with the actual values from the Ultraviolet Imager from the NASA Polar spacecraft UVI. They compared 2194 images from UVI from years 1997 and 1998 for $K_p \geq 3$ and nighttime MLTs (Magnetic local time) between 19:00 and 6:00. In the future, when heliospheric solar wind models improve, these 60 minutes may extend to days [5].

The Wang-Sheeley-Argge-Enlil Cone model which makes space weather predictions could provide with 1 to 4 days predictions of the Coronal mass ejections (CME) directed to the Earth.

Coronal mass ejections are a major component of the solar storms. They interact with the Earth’s magnetic field which produce geomagnetic storms, these can for example cause a disturbance of Earth’s magnetic field.

Figure 3 - (a) UVI observation and (b) Energy flux map from OVATION at the same time (1997)

Other improvements to the OVATION model can be made for low-latitude regions. For MLAT (Magnetic latitude) under 50° there are poor sampling statistics. For these latitudes the model is limited to Kp values higher than 8.

In 2014 was introduced the OVATION Prime 2013 [6] which is an upgrade to the 2010 version. It uses UV images from the GUVI (Global Ultraviolet Imager) instrument on the satellite TIMED for high disturbance levels. This version was tested as well against the hemispheric auroral power data from the UVI. The auroral power, which is predicted by both models is almost identical. One of the most important difference is that the OP-2010 (the previous version) can just show the aurora oval over Kp = 5+ oder 6- at lower latitudes and the OP-2013 shows the aurora oval even when the MLAT is less than 55° or a bit less.

Figure 4 - On the top OVATION Prime has many noises and doesn't show good data for less than 60° MLAT. On the bottom the OVATON Prime 2013 shows a better resolution and goes till 57° MLAT

5 CONCLUSION

Solar activity causes one of the most beautiful natural events in our planet, the Aurora Borealis and the Aurora Australis

but depending on the intensity of it, can be extremely dangerous and catastrophic. There are many organizations around the world working together on the best way to predict this activity and in the worst scenario, allow the human being to be prepared for it. There are many models which already do a very good job but these are still being improved. The NOAA for example expects to eventually use solar observations to predict solar wind conditions in advance.

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